

PROJECT SUMMARY

Instructions:

The summary is limited to 250 words. The names and affiliated organizations of all Project Directors/Principal Investigators (PD/PI) should be listed in addition to the title of the project. The summary should be a self-contained, specific description of the activity to be undertaken and should focus on: overall project goal(s) and supporting objectives; plans to accomplish project goal(s); and relevance of the project to the goals of the program. The importance of a concise, informative Project Summary cannot be overemphasized.

Title: Development of Functional Genomics Tools in Wheat

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Institution: The Regents of the University of California

Mentor: Dubcovsky, Jorge

Institution: The Regents of the University of California

This proposal addresses the following Program Area Priorities: AFRI Challenge Area "Food Security" and AFRI Foundation Area "Plant health and production of plant products".

Together with rice and corn, wheat provides a major source of food to human population. However, the genomic tools in wheat are lacking. This proposal presents a strategy to develop functional reverse genetic tools in tetraploid wheat, bypassing the need of the full genome information. The specific aims include i) characterization of wheat transcriptome, ii) development of exome capture in wheat, iii) applying next-generation sequencing technologies to create a comprehensive, fully-sequenced and publically available mutant library of tetraploid wheat and iv) characterization of functional mutants involved in plant innate immunity. The main product of this study will be a publically available database of sequenced wheat mutants, from which induced alleles of interest can be identified and seeds can be obtained upon request. The long term goal of this project is to provide novel sources of genetic variation in wheat that can be used for breeding. The results of the proposed study will assist basic research in wheat, production of improved wheat products and provide means for engineering durable disease resistance against wheat pathogens. Thus, this proposal directly addresses Program Area Priority of Food Security as well as of Plant Health and Production of Plant Products.